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Blended Learning Technology as a Means of Forming a Professional-Personal Position of a Bachelor Psychologist

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Abstract

The relevance of the paper is due to the modernization of Russian education, which led to the need to train a bachelor-psychologist, focused on the implementation of the professional-personal position formed in the process of learning, capable to self-understanding of innovative technologies, self-development and self-realization in professional activities (Verbitsky, 2016; Komarova, 2012).

The globalization of education is associated with the rapid development of digital technologies and their introduction into the learning process. The focus of training a bachelor-psychologist capable of constructively solving problem situations, flexible overcoming difficulties in relations with others, to self-use of innovative technologies in accordance with the requirements of Federal State Educational Standard (FSES) (2016) has become a priority area of modern education (Leontiev, 1975).

The goal of the paper is to argue the theoretical justification for forming of a bachelor-psychologist's position based on blended learning technology, which is based on the ideas of the theory and practice of organizing the educational process on the basis of blended learning technology (Bath & Bourke, 2014; Fahlvik, 2014; Higgins & Gomez, 2016); Higgins concepts of becoming a professional (Markova, 1990); ideas of subject-making personality (Brushleynsky, 2003; Vyunova, 2014). These trends are more aimed at revealing the problem of forming a professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist on the basis of blended learning technology, revealing the possibilities of "mixing" in the educational process the traditional "live" presentation of information and lectures online, groups of students and interaction of educational subjects in the forum or on the web - conference.

The leading methods of the study are: theoretical (analysis of domestic and foreign psychological and educational literature; systematization of materials on the problem of research, modelling, prediction); empirical (poll, pedagogical experiment); diagnostic (expert assessment method, methods of mathematical statistics, data processing).

Our research is based on the ideas of blended learning technology (Krasnova, 2014; Matukhin, 2015, etc.) as a system consisting of different interconnected parts, integrating forms of learning such as full-time in the classroom, in collaboration (educator and bachelor-psychologist) and self-learning activity (Nikitina, 2013). The materials presented in the paper allow to improve the quality of a bachelor-psychologist training, the blended learning technology developed allows to adapt to the changing conditions of modern reality.

Keywords: blended learning technology, formation, professional personal position, bachelor psychologist, digital means.

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Introduction

New trends in the development of the higher education system have exacerbated the problem of training a bachelor-psychologist with a stable professional and personal position, who is able to constructively solve problem situations, flexibly overcoming difficulties in relationships with others, capable of self-understanding of innovative technologies, self-development, personal mobilization aimed at interaction of fundamental resources and digital technologies.

Global changes in the educational space, the development of digital technologies and their introduction into the learning process are reflected in official documents (Federal State Educational Standard, 2016), which fix the goal of the development of the Russian educational space.

All the abovementioned actualizes the problem of forming a professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist on the basis of blended learning technology. In this regard, the formation of a professional-personal position of bachelor-psychologist using digital resources is a particular priority (Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, 1999).

One of the main theoretical areas on which innovations are carried out in the competence paradigm is the idea of personal development, its professional-personal position, knowledge and understanding the value sense of one's own and others, comparing them with their own worldview and life experience; incorporating a bachelor-psychologist into the context of professional activities; the need for interpersonal interaction of educational subjects in the process of joint learning (training in a group, in dialogue) (Slastenin, 2000).

Analysis of domestic and foreign psychological and educational studies has shown that there is no single interpretation of the concept of "professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist." The studies use

close concepts: "the position of the individual" as a place in a certain specific social structure (Blauberg, 1973); "sense position" in the form of a "sense center," a diagram of understanding the subject, a model of its representation and interpretation, the idea of the subject of personality activity" (Bakhtin, 1986); "professional pedagogical position" as a holistic education, as a system of intellectual, strong-willed and emotional-evaluation relations to the world and professional activities (Slastenin, 2000), "subjective position" as a complex integrative characteristic of the person, reflecting its active-selective, proactive-responsible, transformative attitude to oneself, to activities, to the world and life in general" (Aksjonova, 1998).

Thus, the formation of the professional-personal position of the bachelor-psychologist is considered as an integrative quality of the professional's personality, reflecting selective, proactive-responsible, transformative attitude to oneself, to people, to professional activities, as a system-forming factor of its professional and personal self-development, including a system of stable views and values, ensuring a readiness for successful interaction and cooperation in the information environment, spiritual and self-identification.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the research is to form a professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist based on blended learning technology.

Methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study in this paper is founded on the ideas of- a systemic approach (Blauberg, 1973), allowing to present a holistic set of structural components of the professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist; personal-activities approach (Leontiev, 1975), which allows to consider the formation of a professional-personal position within the system of activity, its genesis, evolution of development; axiological approach (Slastenin, 2000), which allows to consider the professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist as the highest value of society.

Digitalization of education and digital transformations in technology have an impact on the development of a professional-personal position, which aims at developing a digital educational space.

The results of questionnaires of bachelor-psychologists are as follows: 49.9% of respondents have a low level of digital literacy, 27.3% of respondents have a low level of mastery of network training, 39.5% - do not fully own the means of blended learning technology, which does not meet the requirements of the

Federal State Educational Standards (2016), the requirements of the labor market of a bachelor-psychologist. It is impossible to train a bachelor psychologist without a constant addition of knowledge in the field of digital technologies.

The requirements of a bachelor psychologist to master digital technologies were defined: the use of digital resources, blended learning technology, the application of network collaboration, etc.

Analysis of psychological and educational literature on the development of blended learning technology by domestic (Krasnova, 2014) and foreign researchers has highlighted three main components of blended learning: full-time learning (face-to-face), on-line learning (educator-computer-student, student – computer, student – computer - student), self-study learning (Nikitina, 2013); blended learning, in which it is possible to "mix": time (lectures online with traditionally "live" presentation of information), place (groups of students at the university and a meeting in a forum and web conference), means (working with electronic resources, reading printed sources) (Bath & Bourke, 2014). The ideal "mixing" includes three components: visible learning/visible learning (the educator sees the results of his work from the point of view of the learners, and bachelor psychologists perceive themselves from the point of view of the educator), forming the assessment (the constant communication of the educator with the learners for recommendations and control); and the third component is the very mixing of new and traditional technologies (Fahlvik, 2014); combinations of known learning modes with methods technologically mediated (Higgins & Gomez, 2016).

According to the scientific works of Bath and Bourke (2014), Krasnova (2014), Matukhin (2015), Nikitina (2013), Fahlvik (2014), Higgins and Gomez (2016), we define the technology of blended learning a bachelor-psychologist as a system that combines the benefits of teaching in the classroom by means of digital technologies that function in constant interconnection with each other, as the integration of full-time learning in the classroom, learning in collaboration (Nikitina, 2013).

Research methods:

- theoretical (analysis of domestic and foreign psychological and educational literature; systematization of materials on the problem of research, modeling, forecasting);
- empirical (poll, pedagogical experiment);
- diagnostic (expert evaluation method, methods of mathematical statistics, data processing).

Experimental research base. The study was carried out on the basis of the the Voronezh State Pedagogical University Voronezh Economic and Law Institute from 2011 to 2019.

Results

Experimental work on the introduction of the model of forming professional personal position of the bachelor of psychologist was carried out in 3 stages: summative, forming, final.

The objectives of the summative stage of the experiment were identified:

- to identify and substantiate the criteria and indicators of evaluation and formation of the professional-personality position of a bachelor-psychologist;
- to select a set of diagnostic techniques to identify the levels of formation of the professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist;
- to formulate the level and meaningful characteristics of the components of the professional-personal position of the bachelor-psychologist (motivational-value, cognitive, reflexive);
- to analyze the formative stage of the experimental work.

In order to diagnose the formation of a professional-personal position of the bachelor-psychologist, the following criteria of value, knowledge, activity, reflexive were identified and substantiated.

The value criterion is defined by indicators such as the motive of self-affirmation; the need to achieve success in professional activities; the value of the profession of a psychologist for society and its personality (Fetiskin, Kozlov, Manujlov, 2008).

The knowledge criterion is defined by such indicators as: knowledge in the field of psychological and educational activity as an area in which a bachelor-psychologist is self-realization; awareness of perception of professional knowledge; independence and depth of judgment in the field of psychological and educational activity. To determine the level of formation of a professional-personal position, indicators of its knowledgeable criterion the following methods were used: diagnostic tests, scores, exams; diagnosis of the level of partial readiness to professional-educational development (Larichev, 2002; Sidorenko, 2000); test-poll of subjective control (Larichev, 2002).

The active criterion is determined by such indicators as mastering various strategies of professional-personal behavior of a bachelor-psychologist in the field of psychological and educational activities;

conscious choice of the profession of psychologist. To determine the level of formation of a professional-personal position, indicators of its active criterion the following methods were applied: diagnosis of the level of partial readiness to professional-educational development (ability to self-government, contact, flexibility) (Fetiskin, Kozlov, Manujlov, 2008); methodology of diagnosis of the direction of personality (Sidorenko, 2000); assessment of the ability to self-development and self-organization (Sidorenko, 2000).

Reflexive criterion is defined by such indicators as: development of professional self-awareness; self-awareness of a professional; understanding of one's strengths and weaknesses in professional activities. To determine the level of formation of a professional-personal position, indicators of its active criterion the following methods were applied: test on assessing self-control in communication (Fetiskin, Kozlov, Manujlov, 2008; Larichev, 2002; Sidorenko, 2000), diagnostics of stress (Fetiskin, Kozlov, Manujlov, 2008; Larichev, 2002; Sidorenko, 2000), self-assessment of the level of reflexive development (Fetiskin, Kozlov, Manujlov, 2008; Larichev, 2002; Sidorenko, 2000).

Analysis of forming stage of the experiment on the formation of professional-personal position based on mixed learning technology is presented on table 3.

After teaching a bachelor-psychologist using blended learning technology, test, oral survey, a set of tasks, assessing the formation of a professional-personal position, was conducted. The results of the control showed that the level of formation of components of the professional-personal position increased.

Table 1. Results of a forming stage of the experiment

Criteria	Control group			Experimental group		
	Levels			Levels		
	Relatively-sustainable, %	Fairly stable %	Steady %	Relatively-sustainable, %	Fairly stable %	Steady %
Value	46	36	18	26	38	36
Knowledgeable	47	33	20	39	33	28
Active	50	35	15	33	34	33
Reflexive	56	29	15	43	30	27

In the experimental group, the number of bachelors-psychologists with a low level of professional-personal formation has become less: value criterion - from 45% to 20%; knowledgeable criterion - from 48% to 29%; active criterion - from 47% to 23%; reflexive criterion - from 56% to 30%. It should be noted that the number of bachelors-psychologists with average level also increased - from 33% to 39% (value criteria); from 32% to 36% (knowledgeable criterion); from 36% to 38% (active criterion); from 29% to 38% (reflexive criterion of professional-personality position).

The formative stage of the experiment showed that there were changes in the level of the formed criteria in the experimental group from the middle to high, and from low to medium. The level of formation of professional-personal position bachelors-psychologists from the control group was not so significant.

Discussions

As a result, of express diagnostics and the interpretation of the results of the forming stage of the experiment showed that bachelors-psychologists taking part in the experiment are mainly aware of the importance of forming a professional-personal position of a bachelor of psychologist, as well as the influence of information resources on the formation of a professional-personal position in the process of the formative stage of the experiment.

Table 2. Dynamics of professional-personal position formation (%) (during the formative stage of the pilot work)

(SS – summative stage, FS – formative stage)

Criteria	Control Group						Experimental Group					
	Relatively-sustainable, %		Fairly stable %		Steady %		Relatively-sustainable, %		Fairly stable %		Steady %	
	SS	FS	SS	FS	SS	FS	SS	FS	SS	FS	SS	FS
Value	48	43	36	36	16	21	45	20	33	39	22	41
Knowledgeable	56	44	30	35	14	21	48	29	32	36	20	35
Active	52	48	34	36	14	16	47	23	36	38	17	39
Reflexive	58	54	32	28	10	18	56	30	29	38	15	32

The results were tested using the Mann-Whitney Criterion and Wilcoxon's two-sample criterion.

The results of the research are assessed by means of Mann-Whitney's U-Whitney Criterion and Wilcoxon's Double-Selective Criterion presented in the Table 3.

Table 3. Mann-Whitney's U-Whitney Criterion and Wilcoxon's Double-Selective Criterion

Indicator	Value
No.1	35
No.2	35
N	70
R1	1454
R2	1031
R1+R2	2485
N/2 (No.1)	2485
U1	401
U2	824
Uemp	401
Ws	1454
Ws(cp)	1 242,5
SEws	85,1
Z	2,48

According to our data ($z = 2.48$), the zero hypothesis that there is no difference between the levels of formation of the bachelor-psychologist's position in terms of criteria in the control group and the experimental group can be rejected ($p > 0.01$).

In our case, $U_{emp} = 401$ which is less than $U_{cr} = 747$, which statistically confirms the validity of the presence of differences.

Statistical processing of empirical results showed the differences in the formation of the professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist based on the technology of blended learning in control and experimental groups.

After teaching a bachelor-psychologist with the technology of blended learning, the final control was carried out using tests, a set of tasks, checking the formation of the professional-personal position of the bachelor-psychologist on the indicators of the following criteria: value, knowledgeable, active, reflexive. The results of the study showed that the level of professional-personality position formation has significantly improved.

As a result, express diagnostics showed that the bachelors-psychologists, involved in the experiment are mainly aware of the importance of forming a professional-personal position, as well as the impact of blended learning technology on the formation of a professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist, revealing opportunities for asynchronous and synchronous interaction.

The results of the experiment confirm the improvement in the quality of training of a bachelor-psychologists, if "digital technologies are perceived as a necessary component of the readiness to the formation of professional-personal position; the content of the training will be focused on digital skills; blended training will be individualized; organizational forms and teaching methods based on blended learning technology will be aimed at transforming the teaching skills into professional skills" (Markova, 1990). Digital technologies are a mandatory component of the process of forming a professional-personal position, which requires structuring the didactic opportunities of these technologies and identifying appropriate ways of using their means at each stage of training of a bachelor-psychologist (Razinkina, 2005).

The formation of a professional-personal position on the basis of blended learning has shown the effectiveness of its use, which is confirmed by a positive motivation to form a professional-personal position, trust in students in choosing an independent trajectory in self-development and self-determination.

Conclusion

The paper presents the formative stage of the formation a professional-personal position based on blended learning technology, the prospect of digital technologies in the educational environment, the effectiveness of mixed learning technology in the formation of a bachelor-psychologist's professional and personal

position, showing the strengths of electronic learning opportunities, their flexibility, interactivity, individualization, in conjunction with the "emotional component of personal communication.

Blended learning technology that combines online forums, conferences, e-mail communication has contributed to the increase in the overall level of formation of professional personal position. The developed special-practice program (Nikitina, 2013) on the formation of a professional-personal position of a bachelor-psychologist on the basis of blended learning technology includes the algorithm of independent activity that provides individual trajectory for every bachelor psychologist while studying (face-to-face and online modes of work).

The formation of a bachelor-psychologist's position on the basis of blended learning technology was not a static process. It should be noted that the training is quite manageable: it can be influenced; it can be improved. Self-reliance is the basis of the blended learning method, so the independent work of the student must be intensive, focused, but forecasting difficulties can be overcome indirectly by teacher's control and help.

The obvious benefits of blended learning technology are undeniable, but there are some difficulties in implementing it that need to be taken into account: unsuccessful selection of material, preventing communication together the studied material, low level of computer literacy, lack of teachers' motivation for self-education (technophobia), which reduces the motivation to work with these programs, reluctance to change the position of the teacher from the informant to the partner.

In our study of the formation of a bachelor-personality position, the basis of blended learning technology is independent, intensive, purposeful and controlled work of a bachelor-psychologist. The effectiveness of the use of this technology in educational activities is largely determined by the main features of this technology, such as: reliance on a set of interconnected approaches: systemic, personal-active, axiological, contextual, competent; The use of new means of interpersonal interaction, the possibility of objective assessment; developing the ability to plan ones activities, receive and use knowledge outside the classroom, saving classroom time, access to authentic educational materials, accessibility, support for educational autonomy.

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